

AAV-tdTomato Images

Cerebellum

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Cerebellum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Cerebellum

40x

200x

Colon

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Colon

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Colon

40x

200x

Duodenum

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Duodenum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Duodenum

40x

200x

Heart

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Heart

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
Nontransgenic
F55
Heart

40x

200x

Hippocampus

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht

1.5 months

B125

Hippocampus-cluster near cortex

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Hippocampus

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Hippocampus

40x

200x

Ileum

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Ileum

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Ileum

40x

200x

Kidney

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Kidney

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Kidney

40x

200x

Liver

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Liver

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Liver

40x

200x

Lungs

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Lungs

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Lungs

40x

200x

Olfactory Bulb

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Olfactory Bulb

40x

200x

Pancreas

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Pancreas

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Pancreas

40x

200x

Skeletal Muscle

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Skeletal Muscle

40x

200x

Skin

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Skin

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Skin

40x

200x

Spleen

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Spleen

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Spleen

40x

200x

Stomach

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B121
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B125
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
1.5 months
B130
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B122
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B126
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
3 months
B132
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B123
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B128
Stomach

40x

200x

tdTomato/Hoescht
6 months
B133
Stomach

40x

200x